

Deliverable 13.9

M12 Annual webcast and resource document

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Deliverable type	(X)
R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC: Websites, patents, filing, press and media actions, videos, etc	X
OTHER: Software, technical diagram	
DMP: Data Management Plan	
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc	

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1 Introduction and summary

1.1 Purpose of the document

The document describes the implementation of the first webcast and the supporting materials and resource documents created for the action of the Task 13.6

1.2 Summary

During this first period, there have been several actions and materials created for the dissemination with a targeted audience specialized on the PV End-of-Life topic. For the purpose of this document, are described the 3 main actions taken during the period:

- Quasar presentation inside SolarPower Europe “Product Sustainability” workstream
- Open Quasar Webcast
- Web Infographic

2 Description of the actions

2.1 Quasar presentation inside SolarPower Europe “Product Sustainability” workstream

A big effort of coordination with relevant stakeholders on the European PV industry has been done during the period, to create awareness of the project. Being SolarPower Europe one of the main associations on the European PV Industry, was negotiated and agreed to run a presentation of the Quasar Project inside the “Product Sustainability” workstream meetings where Solar Power Europe has more than 250 stakeholders directly related with Sustainability and End-of-Life topics.

On the 29th of April 2025 it was performed a presentation with some background on the PV waste problem, the presentation of the project and project partners, the challenges of the End-of-Life ecosystem, and the objectives of the project to solve these challenges. Also, an invitation to participate in the next Quasar project events open to the public.

In addition to the live presentation during the workstream meeting with more than 100 attendees, post-meeting materials has been distributed through mail to all the SolarPower Europe “Product Sustainability” workstream and shared to other potential target audience through LinkedIn with a reach to about 1000 people.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/alberto-pico-fernandez_quasar-presentation-activity-7325096854096883714-

2.2 Open Quasar Webcast

A webcast was organized by EEU in collaboration with all Quasar members, to disseminate the project description, challenges, objectives, and provide an overview of the last advancements of the project.

The webcast organization was disseminated through previous events (Augsburg Quasar Workshop the week of the Intersolar Munich, and in the presentation to SolarPower Europe “PV Sustainability” workstream) and through Social Media channels of Quasar Project.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/quasar-eu-project_quasar-horizoneurope-solarpv-activity-7323319166675968000-

[SkbS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAYg0OUBVXqcHLz_UnHkPkaPOHAHMBogktY](https://www.linkedin.com/posts/quasar-eu-project_quasar-horizoneurope-solarpv-activity-7323319166675968000-SkbS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAYg0OUBVXqcHLz_UnHkPkaPOHAHMBogktY)

The screenshot shows a LinkedIn post from the Quasar EU Horizon Project. The post title is "QUASAR EU Horizon Project" with 211 followers and 3 weeks old. The main text of the post is: "WEBCAST: Unveiling the Quasar EU Project- An Overview of the European End-of-Life Solar PV Ecosystem". It includes the date "21st May", time "11:30-12:00 CEST", and "Online". A registration link is provided: "Free Registration: https://lnkd.in/d/HCWejHT". The post body text says: "Join us for an engaging webcast introducing the Quasar Horizon Europe Project—a forward-looking initiative tackling the pressing challenges of the End-of-Life (EOL) solar PV module supply chain in Europe." Below this, there is a "Why Attend?" section with bullet points: "Gain insights into the current gaps and challenges in the EOL PV ecosystem", "Explore Quasar's goals to build a more circular, sustainable solar future", "Hear about major milestones and what's ahead", and "Connect with experts and stakeholders driving the industry's change". It also mentions a featured speaker: "Featuring: Alberto Pico Fernández, Technical Leader, EPRI in Europe Europe". A call to action says: "Your participation can help shape the future of solar sustainability. Be part of the dialogue." At the bottom, there are hashtags: "#Quasar #HorizonEurope #SolarPV #EOL #CircularEconomy #Sustainability #SolarInnovation" and a "Mostrar traducción" link.

In addition to the live webcast audience, the webcast has been recorded and uploaded to the EPRI YouTube Channel, where EPRI has more than 8000 subscribers.

https://youtu.be/ZMmacOzUsvM?si=t6NOjD1EiBq_PRF

The YouTube video has been disseminated through the Quasar Project Social Media.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/quasar-eu-project_webcast-unveiling-the-quasar-eu-project-activity-7335249869042860032-q1Ck?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAYg0OUBVXgcHLz_UnHkPkaPOHAHMBogktY

QUASAR EU Horizon Project

213 seguidores

25 minutos • Editado •

Missed our webcast? Watch the replay now! 🔄

The recording of "Unveiling the Quasar EU Project – An Overview of the European End-of-Life Solar PV Ecosystem" is now live on YouTube! 🎥

Led by Alberto Pico Fernández, Technical Leader at EPRI Europe, this 30-minute session dives into the QUASAR Horizon Europe Project, an EU financed initiative focused on building a circular and sustainable End-of-Life (EOL) solar PV ecosystem in Europe.

Key takeaways:

- Insights into the current gaps and challenges in the EOL PV ecosystem
- QUASAR's goals to build a more circular, sustainable solar future
- Major milestones and what lies ahead for each Work Package

🔗 Watch here: <https://lnkd.in/dPJm5SE>

The future of solar isn't just renewable – it's circular. 🌞🔄
Hashtag

[#QUASAR](#) [#HorizonEurope](#) [#SolarPV](#) [#EOL](#)
[#CircularEconomy](#) [#Sustainability](#) [#SolarInnovation](#)
EPRI in Europe Alberto Pico Fernández

Quasar

2.3 Web Infographic

It has been created a web infographic open to the public.

EU Horizon QUASAR Project Objectives

The EU Horizon project QUASAR is dedicated to advancing a circular economy for the solar PV industry. By developing closed-loop systems, enhancing recycling rates, and leveraging digital twins for systematic collection and management, the project targets eco-efficiency improvements of over 70% across the PV end-of-life (EOL) supply chain. To achieve these outcomes, QUASAR sets the following key performance indicators:

- Reduce decommissioning costs by 20%
- Lower module inspection costs to below 5 €/module
- Limit module repair costs to under 7.5 €/module
- Scale up recycling treatment capacity to 10,000 t/year
- Achieve recycling rates of 70-90% for silicon, silver, polymers, and glass

The main topics addresses on the infographic are the next ones:

- EU Horizon QUASAR Project Objectives
- Elements of a Solar PV Circular Economy
- Circularity Strategies for PV Modules
- Opportunities for PV Value Chain Stakeholders to Adopt Circular Strategies
- Material Recovery via Recycling
- Markets for Materials
- Plant Weight Breakdown
- EOL Module Projections
- Plant End-of-Life Options
- EOL Regulatory Requirements
- Options and Prices for EOL PV Module Dispositioning
- R&D Needs

You can access the web infographic from next link:

<https://interactive.epri.com/pv-circularity-quasar/p/1>

